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Dirac operator and differential operator with involution in the lebesgue spaces. Spectral analysis

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Abstract. Dirac operator and differential operator with involution in the Lebesgue spaces is defined, spectrum's asymptotic and equiconvergence of spectral decompositions are obtained.

Keywords: Dirac operator, differential operator with involution, Lebesgue spaces, spectrum of an operator, asymptotic behavior of the spectrum, spectral decompositions, method of similar operators.

Оператор Дирака и дифференциальный оператор с инволюцией в лебеговых пространствах. Спектральный анализ

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Аннотация. В статье определяется оператор Дирака и дифференциальный оператор с инволюцией в пространствах Лебега, получены асимптотика спектра и равносходимость спектральных разложений.

Ключевые слова. Оператор Дирака, дифференциальный оператор с инволюцией, пространства Лебега, спектр оператора, асимптотика спектра, спектральные разложения, метод подобных операторов.

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1. Definition of Dirac operator.

Let us the Dirac operator $L: D(L) \subset L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2) \rightarrow L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2)$, is defined as $Ly = i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \frac{dy}{dt} - vy$, $y \in D(L)$, where $v(t) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & P(t) \\ Q(t) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, $t \in [0, 2\pi]$, $P, Q \in L_\infty([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C})$. Its domain $D(L)$ is determined by periodic boundary condition. Thus, $D(L) = \{y \in W_p^1([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^n) : y(0) = y(2\pi)\}$.

$W_p^1([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2)$ is Sobolev space, that we define as $\{y \in L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2), p \geq 1 : y \text{ is absolutely continuous, } \dot{y} \in L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2)\}$, where $L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^2)$ - Banach space (Lebesgue space) of p degree summable ($p \in [1, \infty)$) on the $[0, 2\pi]$ and with domain \mathbb{C}^2 functions which norm is finite $\|x\|_p = (\int_0^{2\pi} \|x(t)\|_{\mathbb{C}^2}^p dt)^{1/p}$, $t \in [0, 2\pi]$, $L_p[0, 2\pi]$ - Banach space of p degree summable ($p \in [1, \infty)$) functions on the $[0, 2\pi]$.

If $v = 0$ (zero potential), operator L is called free Dirac operator and denoted L^0 . It usually plays the role of an unperturbed operator in our study of operator L while the operator of multiplication by v is regarded as a perturbation.

The operator L^0 has discrete spectrum: $\sigma(L^0) = \mathbb{Z}$, each $\lambda_n = n \in \mathbb{Z}$ is eigenvalue with eigenspace $E_n^0 = \text{Span}\{e_n^1, e_n^2\}$, where $e_n^1 = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\lambda_n t} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$, $e_n^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ e^{i\lambda_n t} \end{pmatrix}$, $t \in [0, 2\pi]$.

Our definitions and notation for operator L mainly follow the papers [4], [5], which also contain some general spectral properties of Dirac operators, but was researched only in Hilbert spaces. The investigation there uses the standard methods of perturbation theory [6] (the resolvent method) and the representation of operators by matrices.

2. Spectral analysis of Dirac operator.

We study spectral properties of Dirac operators using the method of similar operators [1], [2], [7], [8], because any attempt to study the Dirac operator L using the general methods of perturbation theory [6] encounters difficulties caused by the following properties: the distance between the eigenvalues of the unperturbed operator L^0 does not tend to infinity, the perturbation (the operator of multiplication by v) is an unbounded operator.

The idea of this method is to find a similarity transformation of the operator under consideration (the perturbed operator) into an operator which spectral properties are close to those of the unperturbed operator (which is the free operator L^0 in our case). This substantially simplifies the study of L . Thus we denote $L = A - B$, where $A = L_0$ is unperturbed operator, B is the operator of multiplication by v .

The following theorem contains some results for spectrum of Dirac operator.

Theorem 1. [8] Perturbed operator is operator with compact resolvent. There exists the numeration of eigenvalues such that spectrum $\sigma(A - B)$ can be written as

$$\sigma(L) = \sigma_{(m)} \cup \left(\bigcup_{|n| \geq m+1} \sigma_n \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{(m)}$ - finite set, $\sigma_n = \{n + \beta_n^\pm\}$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \beta_n^\pm = 0$, $|n| \geq m + 1$.

Also $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{\lambda'_n + \lambda''_n}{2} - 2n \right| = 0$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, where λ'_n, λ''_n - eigenvalues of operator L .

Next result gives equiconvergence of spectral decompositions for Dirac operator in the Lebesgue spaces.

Theorem 2. [8] There exists equiconvergence of spectral distributions for operators L and L^0 :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\tilde{P}_n - P_n\| = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \tilde{P}_{(m)} + \sum_{|k|=m+1}^n \left(1 - \frac{|k|}{n}\right) \tilde{P}_k - P_{(m)} - \sum_{|k|=m+1}^n \left(1 - \frac{|k|}{n}\right) P_k \right\| = 0, \quad (3)$$

where P_n is the orthogonal Riesz projection corresponding to the one-point set $\{\lambda_n\} \subset \sigma(L^0)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\tilde{P}_{(m)}, \tilde{P}_n, |n| \geq m+1$, - Riesz projections corresponding to the operator L and sets $\sigma_{(m)}, \sigma_n, |n| \geq m+1$.

3. Definition of differential operator with involution.

Let us the differential operator with involution $L: D(L) \subset L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^m) \rightarrow L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^m)$,

is defined as

$$l(y) = y'(x) - Q(x)y(2\pi - x), x \in [0, 2\pi], Q \in L_p([0, 2\pi], \text{End } \mathbb{C}^m),$$

where

$$y \in D(L) = \{y \in W_p^1([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^m): y(0) = y(2\pi)\}.$$

So we can denote differential operator L also as

$$Ly = L^0 y - Vy, \quad (4)$$

where $(L^0 y)(x) = y'(x)$ is unperturbed operator, $(Vy)(x) = Q(x)y(2\pi - x)$, $x \in [0, 2\pi]$, $y \in L_p([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^m)$ is perturbation.

Spectrum of unperturbed operator L^0 consists of eigenvalues $\lambda_n = in, n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Corresponding proper subspace is $E_n^0 = \text{Span}\{e_n^1, \dots, e_n^m\}$, where $e_n^1 = e^{int}e_1, \dots, e_n^m = e^{int}e_m, e_1, \dots, e_m$ - standard basis in \mathbb{C}^m .

To study the spectral properties of the operator L , represented as (4), the method of similar operators [1], [2], [7], [8] is used also.

4. Spectral analysis of differential operator with involution.

Теорема 3. [2] Perturbed operator L is operator with compact resolvent. There exists the numeration of eigenvalues such that spectrum such that spectrum $\sigma(L)$ can be written as

$$\sigma(L) = \sigma_{(m)} \bigcup \left(\bigcup_{|n| \geq m+1} \sigma_n \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_{(m)}$ - finite set, $\sigma_n, |n| \geq m+1$, are defined as

$$\sigma_n = \{in + \alpha_n^\pm\}, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n^\pm = 0.$$

Note that if we consider the potential in space $L_2([0, 2\pi], \mathbb{C}^m)$, then the results of the paper [7] can be used for the asymptotic of the spectrum.

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